

Developing the first astronomical and quantum imaging instrument using the Smart Skipper-CCD technique.

Contribution to the Latin American Strategy Forum for
Research Infrastructure

Thematic areas:

Instrumentation and Computing
Astronomy and Astrophysics
Dark Matter

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Abstract:

Cosmic surveys aim to understand the fundamental physics governing dark energy and dark matter, which together comprise 95% of the Universe. This proposal seeks to develop technology and scientific forecasts for next-generation cosmic surveys probing the ‘dark sector’. Our specific aims are: (1) to develop faster readout strategies for low-noise Skipper CCDs, (2) characterize the optical performance of these detectors for use in quantum imaging applications and cosmic surveys, (3) to demonstrate the first implementation of Skipper CCDs on a prototype astronomical instrument, and (4) to assess the sensitivity of future cosmic surveys to fundamental properties of dark matter.

The non destructive charge sensing capability of the Skipper CCD (compared to the destructive readout of standard CCD [1]) allows to take several measurements of the pixel charge and average them out to get a final value with smaller error. The final error, given by the readout noise (RN), has an inverse relationship with the number of measurements per pixel [2, 3]. Values of 0.1 e⁻ (5-sigma discrimination of single photons) can be achieved for 1000 samples with total readout times in the order of milliseconds. We propose to significantly reduce the readout time by means of an optimization of the number of samples per pixel based on the on-line information from the first measurements of the charge of the pixel. This optimization is implemented on high speed digital processing hardware. For spectroscopy applications, the uncertainty in large charge packets will be dominated by the shot noise from photon absorption so the readout noise requirements can be relaxed (therefore less readout time needed). The technique dramatically reduces the readout time of the Skipper CCD and makes it suitable applications in astronomy and quantum optics. We propose to develop the first instrument for astronomy and quantum imaging applications that uses the smart skipper capability.

List of the interested scientists in the community:

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Current status and expected challenges:

Our group has developed the first and only existing electronics for Skipper-CCD detectors. The good performance results have encouraged its use in more than 10 institutions in United States, Mexico, Canada, Switzerland, Argentina. The readout system provides unique capabilities for low noise applications as required for the Skipper-CCD sensor. With this proposal we want to extent to the ultimate capability of the sensor where the number of samples taken per pixel is an online adaptive algorithm. The optimization uses previous information of the signal to be measured and on chip noise sources, and past information of the samples of the pixel or from previous pixels.

Up to know we have develop the readout system and developed a region of interest algorithms that is suitable for images acquisition resolving with more accuracy certain regions being adaptive image by image.

Objectives:

- Develop the ultimate performance of Skipper-CCD in terms of its readout speed and sensitivity optimization: Smart Skipper-CCD.
- Test its performance for visible light application.
- Build the first camera based on Smart Skipper-CCD.
- Use the new camera for astronomical and quantum imaging applications.

Timeline:

Year 1: Modifications of the hardware and firmware and software to enable full dynamic readout capabilities. In every step test the performance with a Skipper-CCD sensor. Build the the CCD setup. Mechanical and cyro parts.

Year 2: Finish full test of the performance of the readout system. Test full system with a sensor in the setup. Measure readout performance in accuracy vs. readout time of different applications.

Year 3: Develop Smart Skipper-CCD camera. Most of the design of the camera will be similar to the testing setup. Most of the effort will be oriented in the development of the optics.

Year 4: Test instrument with visible light instrumentation. And with laser and not linear optics. Calculate efficiency, quantum efficiency. Develop techniques to analyze the data with position correlation of photons.

Year 5: Install the camera in an astronomical instrument. Analyze the data.

Construction and operational costs:

- Year 1: Construction of the CCD testing setup: 50.000 u\$. Development of hardware, firmware and software by engineers: 15000u\$.
- Year 2: Fellowships and engineering work: 10.000 u\$.
- Year 3: Development of the camera, develop optics: 50.000 u\$.
- Year 4: Buy equipment and instrumentation to test camera to visible light: 20.000u\$. Fellowships: 8.000u\$.
- Year 5: Installation of the camera in an astronomical instrument: 20.000u\$. Fellowships: 10.000 u\$.

Scientific Context:

The non destructive charge sensing capability of the Skipper CCD (compared to the destructive readout of standard CCD [1]) allows to take several measurements of the pixel charge and average them out to get a final value with smaller error. The final error, given by the readout noise (RN), has an inverse relationship with the number of measurements per pixel [2, 3]. Values of $0.1 e^-$ (5-sigma discrimination of single photons) can be achieved for 1000 samples with total readout times in the order of milliseconds. We propose to significantly reduce the readout time by means of an optimization of the number of samples per pixel based on the on-line information from the first measurements of the charge of the pixel. This optimization is implemented on high speed digital processing hardware. For spectroscopy applications, the uncertainty in large charge packets will be dominated by the shot noise from photon absorption so the readout noise requirements can be relaxed (therefore less readout time needed). For Quantum Imaging (QI) applications, the idea is similar, but the uncertainty in the light intensity measurement comes from the quantum efficiency of the sensor (plus inefficiencies of the system).

The technique dramatically reduces the readout time of the Skipper CCD and makes it suitable for these applications in astronomy and quantum optics. Two different scenarios are considered to evaluate the reduction in the readout time for Spectroscopy and QI. In both cases, the total Skipper CCD readout time in regular operation with a root-mean-squared (RMS) RN of $0.1e^-$ for 1000 samples, is compared with the total readout time of the sensor using dynamic scheme.

Spectroscopy: Figure 1a shows one image of the LDSS-3 spectrograph (LDSS:Low Dispersion Survey Spectrograph) for a $4k \times 2k$ CCD. Each line corresponds to a galaxy spectrum. The current readout noise of the instrument is $\sim 5e^-$. For a regular readout with a Skipper CCD (of $0.1e^-$ of RMS) the total readout time is approximately 2.1×10^4 sec. which is prohibited for this application. Using the dynamic readout the sampling number is adjusted keeping the RMS RN negligible compared to the shot noise RMS (RMS RN impact is below 10% of total RMS). Figure 1b shows the required number of samples (in different colors) per pixel for this image. White regions in fig. 1a show high intensity light, while the white regions in fig. 1b are regions where only one sample per pixel is needed. Only a small fraction of the image requires a large number close to 1000. The total readout time reduces to ~ 110 sec. A reduction of more than two orders of magnitude is obtained in this case.

Quantum imaging: In this case, since the shot noise is eliminated by means of the photon entanglement, the dynamic readout is adjusted using the binomial error introduced by the quantum efficiency of the sensor. The CCD we use have good quantum efficiency (~ 0.9) for entangled photon typically used with wavelength around 800 nm. To evaluate the advantage of the adaptive skipper-CCD readout we will use the context provided by recent publications. Current applications like [4] use EMCCD as imagers which has a readout speed of approximately 1 Mpixel/sec. The EMCCD can only count single charge in a pixel without ambiguity. Its separation capability worsen for 2 or more collected charges. This constrains the application to have a flux less than ~ 1 photon/pixel/exposure, to keep the photon coincidence probability low. The skipper CCD allows for

higher fluxes, since it has equal single-count separation for any charge amount in the pixel [2] up to its maximum dynamic range of 10^5 e-. Since the Skipper CCD has slower readout (1 kpixel/sec. for 0.1e- RMS RN), it should work at larger exposure signal to equate the EMCC on-time, ie, approximately 1000 e-/exposure (equal to the rate of the readout times). This simple calculation gives a clear scenario of the intensity regime of the sensor. For typical QI applications, the photon entanglement is used to better deal with objects placed between the light source and the sensor, for example: to measure object properties, correct transmission light medium or secure information transmission, etc. Then, we can assume that the expected intensity in the light signal reaching the Skipper CCD could be any value from 0 to 1000e-/exposure with similar probability. Figure 3c shows a simulation of a Skipper CCD image (with arbitrary 30x15 pixels) under these requirements. In this case the total standard-readout time for negligible RN is 125 sec. Figure 3d depicts the dynamic number of samples per pixel in different colors. Again, pixels values with large charge packets are measured using less time (or less number of samples). In this case the total readout time is reduced to ~ 1 sec, with two order of magnitude in the readout time. For the standard readout is equivalent to have the entire plot in red color.

Methodology:

The work proposed here is divided in three phases of 6 months each. During phase 1 detailed studies of the analog channel chain will be performed for a dynamic pixel readout. During Phase 2, based on the results of phase 1, we will adapt current electronic for the new readout scheme. On phase 3 we integrate the system developed on Phase 2 for an instrument and measure the performance of the dynamic readout using using classical optical sources and entangled photons sources. Optical equipment will be provided by Fermilab.

The readout scheme is dynamically updated with each new pixel sample available. With typical sample rates from 100kHz to 1MHz, the application can only be implemented in embedded digital circuits directly controlling the readout sequence of the signals. This constrain can be perfectly met using a controller (LTA: Low threshold acquisition system) we have just developed for the Dark Matter experiments [5] (the first controller specially designed to operate Skipper CCDs) that uses an FPGA to make the signal controlling. We propose to create a firmware-software framework implemented as an extension of the existing the LTA platform. The digital implementation of the algorithms cover the second stage of the project.

Figure 1. a) Output image from an spectrograph (white means higher intensity regions). b) Number of samples required for negligible RN using dynamic readout(white means only one sample per pixel). c) Simulated image for QI applications (white means higher intensity regions). d) Number of samples required for negligible RN using dynamic readout(white means only one sample per pixel).

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